

Letter from the Editor

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Dear Technician Education Community,

Welcome to Volume 4, Issue 1 of the Journal of Advanced Technological Education (J ATE)!

We are pleased to offer you the release of our seventh publication, Volume 4, Issue 1. What began as an idea to fill a need in our ATE community has grown into a vibrant platform for advancing knowledge in technological education at community and technical colleges—and we have you to thank for being such an integral part of our growth.

This publication would not be possible without the dedicated efforts of our authors, reviewers, editors, staff, and readers. Together, we've created a journal that continues to evolve in both reach and impact. To date, J ATE has published 77 peer-reviewed journal articles by 73 unique contributors, a testament to the strength, depth, and diversity of disciplines within our community.

J ATE was initially launched by the Micro Nano Technology Education Center (MNT-EC), later supported by the J ATE Special Project Grant, and is now proud to be part of a sustainable publishing venture under AdvancedTechMedia LLC (advancedtechmedia.com). This transition has allowed us to maintain our core mission of publishing high-quality, peer-reviewed papers on state-of-the-art research in advanced technology education, while ensuring long-term viability.

We remain committed to open access: manuscript submissions and online publication are still entirely free. Under our new model, however, authors who wish to have their work included in the print editions will need to provide financial support to cover production costs. We invite you to contribute to our next issue. Submissions for Volume 5, Issue 1, are due by January 31, 2026.

We look forward to continuing this journey with your research, your innovations, and your voice.

With gratitude and anticipation,

Peter

Peter D. Kazarinoff

Editor-in-Chief